

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH EMBEDDED LITHIUM-ION POLYMER BATTERIES

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ABSTRACT

Multifunctional composites that combine high load-bearing properties with high electrical energy storage capacity have potential application in next-generation hybrid and electric vehicles. The effect of high structural bending loads on the flexural properties and electrical energy storage capacity of sandwich composites containing lithium-ion polymer (LiPo) batteries embedded within the polymer foam core is explored in this paper. Three-point bend tests which induce failure by cracking of the core are performed on sandwich composites containing single or multiple LiPo batteries. The bending properties of the sandwich material are not changed significantly by embedding batteries within the core. The energy storage capacity of the sandwich composite can be increased by inserting multiple batteries without adversely affecting the bending properties. Furthermore, the internal electrical resistance and capacity of the batteries is not degraded when sandwich composites are damaged by high bending loads.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is exploring new ways to improve the energy efficiency and to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions of cars, busses, trucks and other road vehicles. One approach is to replace components (e.g. body panels and chassis) made of steel with lighter-weight carbon fibre-polymer composite materials, which reduces the fuel consumption and consequently lowers pollution emissions. Another approach is to replace the internal combustion engine with hybrid or electric engines. However, these engines require high capacity electrical energy storage systems; with such systems requiring a large amount of vehicle space and adding greatly to the weight. For example, LMO/NMC batteries used in the all-electric BMWi3 have a total mass of over 200 kg, which accounts for 17% of the curb-side vehicle weight. As another example, the battery system for the Tesla S is 540 kg, which is about 25% of the vehicle weight.

There is growing interest in embedding batteries within vehicle body structures to provide the dual functions of load-bearing and energy storage [1]. In particular, the integration of batteries into composite materials to create energy storage components is a promising approach for next-generation hybrid and electric vehicles. It is usually necessary to remove some of the fibre reinforcement to accommodate the batteries, and this reduces the stiffness, failure stress and other mechanical properties of the laminate material [2]. An alternate approach is to embed the batteries inside the core of sandwich composites, thereby leaving the load-bearing face sheets unaffected.

Numerous studies have investigated the mechanical and dynamic properties as well as the energy storage capacity of monolithic fibre-polymer laminates containing embedded batteries [2-4]. Similar work has been performed for sandwich composites containing embedded batteries [3, 5-8]. For example, Thomas et al. [7] measured an 20% increase to the flexural modulus and a 57% reduction to

the flexure failure stress of sandwich composites when two LiPo batteries were embedded within the core. The large reduction in flexural strength was attributed to premature debonding failure caused by uneven adhesive layers within the sandwich material. Other researchers report similar flexural strengths for sandwich composites with and without embedded LiPo batteries [6, 8]. The internal resistance of the battery has been shown to remain unchanged [5, 6, 8, 9] or increased [5, 6] under bending loads. Aside from flexural properties, it has been shown that embedding batteries in the core of sandwich composites can have a significant adverse effect on the edgewise compression properties, and, to a lesser extent, the tensile properties [6].

Despite the previous studies, it is not known whether the inclusion of batteries within the core of sandwich composites affects core dominated failure modes caused by flexural loadings. The effect of the number and distribution of batteries within the core has also not previously been studied. The aim of the study presented in this paper is to investigate the effect of embedded LiPo batteries on the bending properties and core dominated failure modes of sandwich composites. Core dominated failure modes can occur in engineering applications of sandwich composites subjected to bending. The sandwich material studied consisted of thin face sheets of carbon-epoxy laminate and a thick core of polymer foam, and this type of composite is used in selected automotive components for light-weighting. The bending load case was examined because many automotive components, such as the chassis, are subject to this loading. In this study, we investigated the influence of the number and distribution of embedded batteries on the response of the sandwich composite to high bending load cases which induce core failure by cracking. Sandwich composites can also fail in other modes, such as skin wrinkling, skin fracture or skin-core debonding, although these were not considered as part of this study. This paper focusses on failure initiated within the core (i.e. cracking) where the batteries are located. The effect of high bending loads on the energy storage capacity and internal resistance of the batteries when embedded with sandwich composite materials are also investigated.

2 MATERIALS & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite Materials and Batteries

The sandwich composite material consisted of thin face sheets of carbon-epoxy laminate covering a thick core of polymer foam. The sheets were made of plain weave T300 carbon fabric (200 g/m²) (AC220127 supplied by Colan Ltd) and a low-temperature cure two-part bisphenol-A based epoxy resin (resin-105 and hardener-206 supplied by West System). The core was closed cell PVC foam with a density of 100 kg/m³ (Divinycell H100).

The LiPo batteries are 40 mm long, 30 wide and 4 mm thick and weigh ~10 grams. The batteries are manufactured and supplied by the LiPol Battery Co. Ltd. Each battery was enclosed within a thin protective aluminium pouch. The capacity and voltage of the as-received battery was 500 mAh and 3.7 V, respectively, and the minimum and maximum discharge voltages were 2.7 V and 4.2 V, respectively.

Prior to manufacturing the sandwich composites, a section of the foam core the same size as the battery was cut-out. Insulated copper wiring was soldered to the connections of the battery using 60/40 lead tin solder. This enabled electrical testing once embedded within the foam core. The battery and wiring were inserted into the cut-out section to the foam core, as shown in Fig. 1. After battery insertion, two plies of carbon fabric were placed on both surfaces of the foam core and then wetted with the liquid epoxy resin to create the face sheets. The warp and weft tows to the fabric were aligned along the length and width of the sandwich panels, respectively. Care was taken to ensure both the foam and batteries were also wetted-out with the liquid epoxy resin before application of the face sheets.

Figure 1: Top-view of PVC foam core with two embedded batteries prior to fabrication of sandwich composite. The batteries and leads reside within cut-outs in the foam.

The sandwich composite was cured at room temperature, with no heat or pressure applied to avoid damage to the batteries. The final thickness of the sandwich composites (with or without batteries) was 5.5 mm, with each face sheet being 0.75 mm thick and the core being 4 mm thick. The battery bonded to both the core and face sheets, although narrow resin-rich regions were detected along the core/battery interfaces.

Sandwich composite specimens were made without a battery (control material), one battery or two batteries aligned in series (with a separation distance of 10 or 40 mm). The arrangement of the batteries in the core is illustrated in Fig. 2. The properties of the face sheet laminate, foam core material and LiPo battery are provided in Table 1. Note that the mechanical properties of the LiPo battery are approximations based on experimental data in [10].

Figure 2: Schematic (top and centre section views) of the sandwich specimens showing the distribution of embedded batteries for (a) one battery, (b) two batteries – 10 mm spacing, (c) two batteries – 40 mm spacing. All dimensions in mm.

Property	CFRP [11]	PVC foam [12]	LiPo battery [10]
Density, ρ	1,550 kg/m ³	100 kg/m ³	2,080 kg/m ³
Young's Modulus, E	45 GPa	95 MPa	150 MPa
Compression strength, σ	300 MPa	1.6 MPa	1.0 MPa
Shear modulus, G	3.9 GPa	25 MPa	300 MPa
Shear strength, τ	42 MPa	1.3 MPa	35 MPa

Table 1: Properties of the constituent materials used in the sandwich composites. Mechanical properties measured along the principle bending load direction.

2.2 Flexural test methods

Three-point bend tests were performed on the sandwich specimens based on ASTM D790 [13] (Fig. 3). The specimens were beam-shaped with a total length of 250 mm and width of 50 mm. The bend tests were performed using the support span length of 200 mm, which resulted in the span-to-thickness ratio of 36-to-1. The span caused the specimens to fail by core cracking. The span of 200 mm was sufficient to determine the equivalent flexural stiffness and failure stress of the specimens. The equivalent flexural strength σ_{max} , and equivalent flexural modulus E , of the sandwich composites were calculated using:

$$\sigma_{max} = (3P_{max}L) / (2b(2t+c)^2) \quad (1)$$

$$E = (L^3m) / (4b(2t+c)^3) \quad (2)$$

where b is the specimen width, t is the face sheet thickness, c is the core thickness, P_{max} is the maximum applied load and m is the slope of the initial linear region of the load-displacement curve.

The three-point bend tests were performed at a load point displacement rate of 2 mm/min using a 50 kN Instron test machine. Four specimens of each design shown in Fig. 2 were tested along with the sandwich material without a battery.

Figure 3: Schematic of three-point bend test with applied load P .

2.3 Battery tests

The electrical performance of the LiPo batteries embedded within the sandwich specimens was monitored during and after the three-point bending tests. Cyclic charge-discharge tests were performed using a Cellpro PowerLab 6 multi-chemistry battery workstation. These tests were performed using a constant 1C rate (500 mAh⁻¹) at room temperature. During cycling, the peak voltage, current, internal resistance and cell capacity were measured at ten second intervals. Each battery tested was cycled five times in total, and therefore any change in performance can be attributed to damage caused by the three-point loading, rather than by ageing effects that can occur with LiPo batteries [14].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical Properties of Sandwich Composites with Embedded Batteries

The bending load vs centre-point displacement curves for the sandwich beams with and without batteries are presented in Fig. 4. The flexural modulus and failure stress values for the sandwich specimens are given in Table 2. The flexural modulus of the sandwich beam was not changed by the insertion of one battery, and only a small average stiffness reduction (of ~10%) occurred with two batteries. Within the bounds of experimental scatter, the batteries did not affect the ultimate failure stress of the sandwich beams. The results in Table 2 show that embedding one or two batteries within the foam had little effect on the bending modulus and no effect on the bending failure stress. In all cases, the sandwich specimens failed by core cracking followed by fracture of the skin sheet, as shown for example in Fig 5. The cracking within the sandwich beams containing batteries always occurred along the core/battery interface, as illustrated in Fig 5b. Cracking occurred at the interface due to locally high stress concentrations caused by the large difference in the stiffness properties of the foam core (95 MPa) and the battery (150 MPa) as well as the presence of resin-rich regions. The presence of the batteries within the sandwich core also creates a geometric discontinuity which can also raise the bending stress. However, this did not alter the failure stress or failure mode of the core, further revealing the insignificant influence of batteries.

Figure 4: Representative load-displacement curves for the sandwich composites in three-point bending.

No. embedded batteries	Spacing between batteries (mm)	Apparent flexural strength, σ_{max} (MPa)	Specific strength, σ_{max} / ρ (%)	Apparent flexural modulus, E (GPa)	Specific stiffness, E / ρ (%)
0	-	108 ± 6	100	12.8 ± 0.9	100
1	-	113 ± 2	84	12.8 ± 0.5	80
2	10	109 ± 4	65	11.5 ± 0.3	58
2	40	101 ± 10	61	11.6 ± 0.3	59

Table 2: Flexural properties of sandwich composite specimens.

Figure 5: (a) Cracking failure of foam core and face sheet in the sandwich composite. (b) Schematic showing cracking of the foam core along the boundary with a battery.

3.2 Battery Efficiency in Sandwich Composites under Bending Loads

The internal resistance and capacity of the battery before and after testing is shown in Fig. 6. The performance of the battery was not significantly affected by cracking along the boundary to the foam core under the test condition. This reveals that the LiPo battery used here retains its performance even though the surrounding sandwich composite is severely damaged.

Figure 6: (a) Internal resistance and (b) cell capacity of a single LiPo battery embedded within the sandwich composite pre- and post-flexural testing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Embedding small LiPo batteries within the foam core of sandwich composite materials does not have a large adverse effect on the stiffness and strength properties. The inclusion of one or more batteries had little or no detrimental effect on the bending stiffness of the sandwich composite. Similarly, the maximum strength of the sandwich composites was not affected by batteries when failure occurs by cracking of the core. The internal resistance, capacity and voltage charge/discharge properties of the LiPo battery were not altered from bending loading, even under severe conditions causing the foam core to crack.

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